

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Ideal typology of Multilevel Governance strategies

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1. Introduction

The EU funded research project ROBUST aims to address the fact that poly-crises and heightened turbulence seem to have become the new normal. For decades crises and rising turbulence were relative rare, occasional, and short lived, and dealt with through expert-driven crisis management that quickly restored normalcy. Now we are facing a new predicament where crises are increasingly frequent, multiple, overlapping, and mutually reinforcing and seem to trigger unpredictable dynamics 'where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways (Ansell & Trondal, 2018). The ROBUST project claims that we are living in times of heightened *turbulence* that calls for *robust governance* that allows us to maintain some degree of *stability* in the fundamental values, goals, and functions of public governance if we are *changing* the modus operandi of the public sector by means of adaptation and innovation that might open up new possibilities and bring us to a new and better place. As such, the ROBUST project builds on the assumption that the choice for public leaders and governors is not between stability and change, but between different combinations of stability and change that mutually support each other (Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2023).

The overall purpose of WP3 to broaden our understanding of how multilevel governance can help or hinder robust responses to crisis and heightened turbulence in policymaking processes. Multilevel governance has been often described by policy scholars as a mode or instance of policymaking facilitating problem-solving through the interaction and collaboration of public authorities and key non-public stakeholders at different levels of governance (see e.g.: Piattoni 2010; Maggetti and Trein 2019). WP3 aims to create an ideal typology of strategies for achieving the necessary interactivity within multilevel governance arrangements during moments of crisis to achieve robust responses to the crisis and the turbulence that come with it. Furthermore, WP3 aims to assess this typology vis-à-vis examples of interactivity in multilevel governance arrangements to better understand which configurations or varieties of multilevel governance can support (or hinder) robust crises responses.

This WP3 report provides a systematic literature review with the aim of conceptualizing modes of interactivity within multilevel governance arrangements and policymaking processes, and assessing the potential contribution of different modes or varieties of multilevel governance interactions to robustness (D3.1). A subsequent WP3 report will examine concrete examples of multilevel governance arrangements that supported (or did not support) robust crisis responses in relation to the COVID-19, the financial and the refugee crises in the ROBUST case countries (D3.2).

1.1 Note on methods

The objectives of this report have been pursued by applying sound methods that aim to secure research quality and replicability.

First, we have carried out a systematic analysis of the more cited and accredited literature reviews on multilevel governance which have been published in the last decade, starting from the key reference book of Simona Piattoni (2010), *The Theory of Multilevel Governance*, published by Oxford University Press, to more recent articles taking different theoretical perspectives on multilevel governance (see e.g.: Tortola 2017; Alcantara and Nelles 2014 Stephenson 2013; Bache et al. 2016; Bache, Bartle and Flinders 2016), either as a system or a policymaking arrangement as we will see below.

Second, we searched Google Scholar and Scopus for further studies regarding more specifically multilevel governance in the context of research on emergency management and emergency response policies.

Third, to strengthen the completeness and policy relevance of the study, we have consulted the webpages of the OECD Multilevel Governance and Decentralization unit¹ and established directed contacts with the OECD expert team. In February 2023 a member of the Unito Research Unit has taken part as observer to the Joint CEB-OECD meetings on Local Integration of Refugees, examining the role of local authorities in the multilevel governance of refugee reception.

However, the goal of this literature review is not simply to provide a complete picture of existing research, but also to conceptualize interactivity in multilevel governance and its potential contribution to robustness. This is a particularly crucial point since, in the perspective of the ROBUST Project, since robust responses to crises should not only contribute to alleviate turbulence, but reinforce democracy core values and norms (see Deliverable D2.1 – Proof of concept). Hence, as a fourth step, a further search has been carried out on Google Scholar and Scopus for books and articles combining the keywords ‘multilevel governance’ and ‘democracy’, with the goal of identifying the key dimensions underlying an ideal typology of strategies for achieving the necessary interactivity within multilevel governance arrangements favouring the emergence of robust responses during moments of crisis.

1.2 Structure of the report

The Report has five sections. *Section 2* is devoted to the discussion of the concept of multilevel governance, with the goal of identifying the main uses and approaches characterizing the existing literature. More specifically, we identify four approaches: 1) multilevel governance as dispersion of state authority; 2) the system approach to multilevel governance; 3) the instance of policymaking approach; and 4) multilevel governance as intergovernmental coordination. We contend that the operational definition of multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking is the best suited for the purposes of this Report that seeks to build the theoretical premises for the analysis of the links between multilevel governance and robust responses to crises.

Section 3 provides a literature review of the uses of the concept of multilevel governance in the more specific debate on emergency response policies.

Section 4 introduces our analysis of the nexus between multilevel governance and robustness by considering the debate on the potential trade-offs in multilevel governance policymaking between problem-solving capacity and democratic accountability (Papadopoulos 2007 and 2010; Maggetti and Trein 2019). These critiques of multilevel governance are of a crucial relevance for the theorization of the nexus with robust governance perspective, that aims “to effectively solve emerging problems and challenges while ensuring broad-based support to the changing solutions as well as to the overall system of governance” (Deliverable 2.1, p. 39). To this end – we argue – we need a theoretical framework enabling us to *identify possible configurations or varieties of interactivity in multilevel governance that can potentially contribute to the robust governance of crises by ensuring at the same time that efficient solutions are pursued and principles of democratic legitimacy and accountability are fulfilled.*

¹ See: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/urban-rural-and-regional-development/oecd-multi-level-governance-studies_2414679x

Sections 5 and 6 are devoted to the elaboration of such a theoretical framework. Section 5 presents and operationalizes the four key dimensions of interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking. On this basis, we build a typology of possible variants and ideal-type configurations of multilevel governance. Hence, in section 6, we delve deeper into the discussion of the ideal-types of *centralized* and *decentralized multilevel governance*, and present our hypotheses on the relations with the robust governance of turbulence.

In the conclusion we summarize key findings and discuss the steps forward.

2. Multilevel Governance: what is it?

The objective of this section of the Report is to discuss the generic and operational definitions of multilevel governance that we find in the literature and to clarify our definition and approach to multilevel governance as interactivity. This is a particularly complicated task because of the ongoing discussions on the concept of multilevel governance that, rather than contributing to clarification, seem to have fuelled increasing definitional confusion (see e.g.: Peters and Pierre 2004; Piattoni 2010; Tortola 2017).

In fact, different uses of multilevel governance can be found in the literature. At a more generic and abstract level, multilevel governance has been defined as *dispersion of authority* (Hooghe and Marks 2001). Hence, *the generic definition of multilevel governance alludes to processes of dispersion of state authority leading to increasing multilevelness and complexity in contemporary political systems*. In this rather unspecified meaning, multilevel governance is used as synonymous with multilevel politics (Scholten 2013) and has often been the object of sharp criticism. As Peters and Pierre (2004, 88) sentence, “any complex and multi-faceted political process can be referred to as multilevel governance.”

However, the notion of multilevel governance has also acquired more specific meanings, reflecting the theoretical elaborations taking place in two main strands of literature within political science, i.e.: 1) studies on systems of government, and more specifically on the European integration and federalism; 2) research on policy networks and modes of governance. Here below we briefly illustrate the debate and the ensuing definitions of multilevel governance characterising each research strand. Rather than aiming at establishing a unique and uncontroversial definition of multilevel governance, we start from the assumption that different approaches to multilevel governance may serve different – legitimate – theoretical and analytical purposes, which need to be spelled out and made explicit. Hence, in the final sub-section we clarify our positioning with respect to ongoing debates on multilevel governance, and how the specific definition of multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking can speak to research on robust governance in times of crises.

2.1 Multilevel governance as dispersion of state authority and new system of power allocation

The generic definition of multilevel governance as ‘dispersion of state authority’ reflects the premises of the original use of the term by Gary Marks in 1993 to make sense of a series of structural developments in the process of European integration that pointed to the emergence as a *sui-generis* multilevel polity (for recent reviews, see: Stephenson 2013; McNamara, 2018). More specifically, with the Single European Act of 1986 and the Maastricht Treaty of 1991, a process of increasing

institutionalisation of the regional dimension of European policies had started to take place, leading to the creation of a new cohesion fund and to the strengthening, on the one hand, of regions' competences in the programming and implementation of structural funds and, on the other, of the Commission's planning powers (see also: Hooghe 1996). The label 'multilevel governance' was used by Marks (1993) to characterise the European Community of the time as a system of "continuous negotiation among nested governments at different territorial tiers" (402).

In other words, the unfolding European polity was conceived by Marks as ontologically different from other types of multilevel political systems like federations or confederations because of the particular pattern of state authority dispersal which implied overlapping competences among multiple levels of government interacting with each other.

Subsequent elaborations of the concept of multilevel governance always by Marks (1996) and then also in collaboration with Lisbet Hooghe, seem to point to a broadening of its scope of empirical application, from the European Community to other multilevel polities (Piattoni 2010; Tortola 2017). A case in point is their definition of multilevel governance as "the process of dispersion of authority away from the nation state across interdependent and yet autonomous public authorities and non-public organisations at different levels of government" (Hooghe and Marks 2001, xi). In this new conceptualisation of multilevel governance as a *system of state power allocation*, the concomitant presence and interaction of state and non-state actors at different levels of government is brought to the fore. In other terms, in multilevel governance systems state authority is increasingly dispersed not only across different governmental authorities, but also among different types of non-governmental actors that not only have an interest in the issue at hand, but can also contribute to policymaking by providing resources that public institutions do not have. Depending on issue, private companies, trade unions, non-governmental organisations, banking foundations etc., can become key partners in policymaking processes. According to Bache and Flinders (2004a), multilevel governance is characterised by interactions and interdependencies that span across both the vertical/intergovernmental and the horizontal/state-society dimensions of policymaking processes.

However, as noticed by Tortola (2017), theoretical elaborations of multilevel governance as a *system of state authority allocation* have paid little – if any – attention to the horizontal dimension of multilevel governance, *the facto* assigning greater prominence to the vertical/intergovernmental dimension and to the analysis of formal structures of division of competence across different types of jurisdictions. This is clearly reflected in Hooghe and Marks' (2003) theorisation of two sub-types of multilevel governance intended as systems of state authority allocation characterised by different constitutional designs and legal jurisdictions. More specifically, sub-type I describes a governing system based on a limited number of clearly defined non-overlapping territorial jurisdictions, each with a 'bundle' of functions, essentially mirroring federalist systems; while sub-type II is defined as a more anarchical order of single-purpose or task-specific jurisdictions with overlapping memberships.

Multilevel governance as a new system of state authority allocation or of governing in multilevel systems has become increasingly debated in the context of globalisation studies, as a benchmark to assess global governance structures (Zürn 2011), as well as in the literature on problem-solving in federalist polities (Scharpf 1997; 2001; Benz 2000; Behnke, Broschek, and Sonnicksen 2019) and in unitary countries like the UK (Bache and Flinders 2004b). However, other authors contend that the EU should continue to represent the primary – if not exclusive – empirical referent of the notion of multilevel governance (Tortola 2017; Stephenson 2013), while other concepts like intergovernmental relations (IGR), appear more suited to reflect the development of governance relations in non-European polities like the United States (Ongaro et al. 2010, 2).

To encompass these various research streams and theoretical elaborations, recently Hooghe, Marks and Schakel (2016; 2020) have defined multilevel governance as *dispersion of authority whether this is within a state or beyond it*, reflecting both processes of internationalisation/Europeanization and decentralization. In this perspective, the concept of multilevel governance transcends the divide between unitary and federalist states, because it reveals a process of power rescaling and increasing multilevelness that is not necessarily anchored to constitutional rules (2019, 199).

The definition of multilevel governance as rescaling of state authority and political power underlies also critical (urban) governance studies (see e.g., Jessop 2004) and research on the restructuring of the welfare state (Kazepov 2010). A leitmotif in these streams of literature is the functionality of state rescaling processes to the logic of capitalist accumulation, and therefore an understanding of multilevel governance as re-definition and adaptation of national states' role and functions to the pressures of neo-liberal globalisation. Compared to studies on multilevel governance in the EU, critical approaches pay greater attention to non-state actors in the context of dynamics of privatization and subsidiarization of social policy (see e.g.: Kazepov 2010), as well as of mobilisation of economic resources for the sake of local development and cities' competition for international investments (see e.g., Brenner 2004).

To sum up, the debate on MLG as dispersion of authority and rescaling of state power has led to an understanding of MLG as a macro-process responding – primarily – to (top-down) processes of economic and political restructuring, as well as to (bottom-up) pressures for decentralization. The focus of theoretical elaborations and empirical analyses lies predominantly on the vertical/intergovernmental dimension and on the changing design of jurisdictional structures, while the study of concrete interactions and dynamics of policymaking in systems of multilevel governance seems to have been limited to (critical) studies of welfare state restructuring. With respect to EU integration studies, an exception can be considered the study of Piattoni (2010) on multilevel governance within the specific policy sectors of regional development, environment and higher education, which shows however an understanding of multilevel governance closer to the instance approach that we will examine more in-depth below.

2.2 Multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking or mode of governance

Departing from Hooghe and Marks' definition of MLG as “the process of dispersion of authority away from the nation state across interdependent and yet autonomous public authorities and non-public organisations at different levels of government” (Hooghe and Marks 2001, xi), a new wave of conceptualisation of MLG as an *instance of policymaking* has been put forward by North American scholars working at the intersection of public policy analysis, new public management (NPM) and local governance studies. As explained by Alcantara and colleagues (Alcantara and Nelles 2014; Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016), whereas debates on European integration and state redefinition viewed multilevel governance as a new emerging *system* of authority and power allocation, the conceptualization of multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking shifts the attention to the relations taking place in policy processes on specific issues. This intrinsically relational perspective not only takes the horizontal dimension – more – seriously into consideration, but enables the concept to travel across different multilevel political systems, stimulating new research and speculation on the concrete factors and mechanisms driving the occurrence of MLG policymaking (Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016).

Operational definitions of MLG as a specific *instance or configuration of policymaking in multilevel political settings* (Piattoni 2010; Scholten 2013; Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016; Caponio and Jones-Correa 2018) converge in identifying *three key features of MLG: 1) different levels of*

government are simultaneously involved; 2) non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved; 3) relationships between different levels of government and with non-governmental actors take the form of non-hierarchical networks based on cooperation and consensus building.

Whereas criterion 2 clearly asserts that instances of multilevel governance do not have to be confused with instances of intergovernmental relations (Alcantara and Nelles 2014), criterion 3 draws attention to the type of relationships that characterise multilevel governance as a specific mode of policymaking, i.e. non-hierarchical and cooperative relations *in both* the intergovernmental/vertical and the state-society/horizontal dimensions. As such, multilevel governance is likely to coexist with other possible modes of policymaking characterised by different levels of cooperation (or a lack thereof) in the vertical and/or horizontal dimensions (see also: Scholten 2013; Caponio 2022a).

Research on multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking has been particularly influential in Canada and the United States, where scholars have used the notion of multilevel governance to capture the functioning of concrete processes of policymaking and multi-layered policy dynamics unfolding in the context of these two federalist systems (for Canada see: Gagnon 2018; for the US: Agranoff 2018). In the Canadian context, research studies on multilevel governance arrangements have regarded such different policy issues such as relations with indigenous communities (Alcantara and Nelles 2014; Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016; Papillon 2012), educational policies (Tamtik and Colorado 2022) and transport infrastructures (Sutcliffe 2012) among others. With respect to the United States, the notion of multilevel governance has been used primarily to make sense of the mobilisation of municipal authorities in face new challenges for urban governance and local communities, including access to social assistance, drug addiction, immigrant integration etc. (see: Agranoff 2018; Kaufmann and Sidney 2020).

In a similar vein, also in Europe the understanding of multilevel governance as a specific instance or mode of policymaking underlies studies on local/regional policy processes on such different issues as environment and climate change mitigation (Benz et al. 2015; Gustavsson, Elander and Lundmark 2009; Kern and Bulkeley 2009), regional policies of economic development (Ravazzi 2018), migration (Scholten 2013; Caponio 2018 and 2021a; Scholten et al. 2018), urban development and internationalization (Pierre 2019; Mocca 2019). With respect to EU policymaking, the instance approach to multilevel governance has been applied primarily to the study of cohesion policy (see e.g.: Dąbrowski, Bachtler and Bafoil 2014), social policy and the Urban Method of Coordination (Curry 2016), environment and climate change mitigation (Behnke, Broschek, and Sonnicksen 2019), high level education (for a comparison of multilevel governance in all these three policy fields, see: Piattoni 2010), and refugees and asylum seekers reception (Caponio and Ponzio 2022; Caponio 2022b).

A key question underlying the debate especially in Europe, regards the explanatory factors and mechanisms that allow for the emergence of multilevel governance policymaking arrangements. Studies regarding the EU level have emphasised the importance of contextual factors like national/regional institutions and political cultures, that can either favour or hamper multilevel governance interaction (Dąbrowski, Bachtler and Bafoil 2014). However, Piattoni (2010) contends that also relational factors matter, and more specifically the intensity of the relations between subnational institutions and civil society associations, while, in the case of climate change mitigation networks, the local structure of private companies appear of a key relevance (Gustavsson, Elander, and Lundmark 2009). With respect to the highly pitched issue as migration, the public opinion mood as perceived by politicians seems to have played a key role in constraining multilevel governance relations in the aftermath of the 2015 crisis (Caponio and Ponzio 2022), whereas, at the local level, political actors emerge as central agents in shaping multilevel governance policymaking (Scholten et

al. 2018). Governmental actors seem to play a decisive role also in EU multilevel governance arrangements like the Open Method of Coordination (Curry 2016). In other words, multilevel governance arrangements appear very often to take place in the 'shadow of hierarchy' (Börzel 2010), that is when governmental actors show interest and willingness to lend legitimacy to multilevel networks and venues (see e.g., Alcantara and Morden 2019 on indigenous multilevel governance in Canada; Caponio 2021 and 2022a on city networks on migration in the EU and the United States).

2.3 Multilevel governance in policy relevant debates. The work of OECD

Parallel to scholarly debates in political science, European integration theory and governance studies reviewed above, the concept of multilevel governance represents also a widely accepted idea in political and administrative circles. Especially in the EU, the notion of multilevel governance is often evoked by official documents, policy briefs and expert reports as a benchmark for good practices in policy making and implementation. A recent case in point is the Urban Agenda for the EU, described in its constitutive document, the so-called Pact of Amsterdam, as a venue offering "a new form of multilevel and multi-stakeholder cooperation with the aim of strengthening the urban dimension in EU policy" (Council of the European Union 2016).

Of a key relevance for policymakers and practitioners' debates on multilevel governance is the work developed by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development OECD, and more specifically by the Regional Development Policy Committee (RDPC) created in 1999, and then renamed Multilevel Governance and Decentralization unit². Such work very much connects multilevel governance and decentralisation. According to the website of the OECD, the work of the organization is meant to "provide international benchmarks based on statistics, analysis and good practices" and, more specifically, to "help countries respond to diverse challenges that can affect how policy is implemented by subnational levels of government, such as the assignment of responsibilities, subnational finance and investment, coordination of institutions and improving capacity".

As part of its 'studies on multilevel governance' OECD has published a number of reports in the past decade, which cover a wide range of issues (e.g., finance, migration, development etc.), and place a primary focus on different levels of government (e.g., some reports focus specifically on the regional level, others on the local level). Two reports are particularly interesting as they reveal the organization's conceptualisation of the MLG concept: the OECD Report on Multilevel Governance Reforms (OECD, 2017), and the OECD Report on Regional Governance (OECD, 2022), which contains a specific section on "multilevel governance tools" and particularly on tools that enable "sound governance".

Four key insights can be derived from such reports. First, the OECD seems to conceptualise MLG as a policy process that is specifically related to policy implementation rather than decision-making. Many of its reports focus on the division of competences among (governmental) actors located at different levels. One of the key challenges that the organization has tried to address in its work concerns the complexity of the "assignment of responsibilities" to different governments which "often leads to competing and overlapping competencies as well as a lack of clarity on 'who does what' across levels of government" (see OECD 2017).

² This can be accessed at this webpage: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/urban-rural-and-regional-development/oecd-multi-level-governance-studies_2414679x

Second, the OECD seems to conceptualise MLG as a top-down process. The OECD explicitly defines its role as that of assisting national governments that “seek guidance in making decentralisation and territorial reforms happen” (OECD Website³).

Third, the OECD seems to conceptualise MLG as a process that involves mostly the vertical dimension. The overarching description of the OECD’s work on MLG in the organization’s website suggests that this work is concerned with “co-ordination arrangements between national, regional and local governments, as well as across jurisdictions, are needed, along with subnational capacity building”. Most of the reports produced by the OECD focus on relations between national, regional and local governments. Occasionally the OECD reports refer to the involvement of non-public actors – mostly described as “stakeholders”. For instance, in its 2022 Report, the OECD provides some “tools for stakeholder concertation and participation to ensure the success of place-based policies” but these tools are not linked to previous reflections on vertical cooperation arrangement.

Fourth, the OECD seems to conceptualise MLG as a mostly formal process. Overall, many of the OECD reports on MLG focus on ‘multilevel governance reforms’, such as those implemented in Finland, France, Italy, Japan and New Zealand in the past two decades. The 2017 report explicitly looks at “institutional reforms, which reorganise powers, responsibilities and resources across levels of government, as well as territorial reforms, which address territorial structures, often modifying regional and local government administrative areas”. Very rarely the organization refers to informal arrangements.

2.4 Definitions of multilevel governance. An assessment

From the literature review carried out above, at least four definitions of multilevel governance emerge. Each one is the result of different, theoretical and/or policy debates, therefore serving different purposes. In this sub-section we briefly discuss each definition to assess their potential to contribute to the theorization of robust governance in times of turbulence.

The first definition is the very generic one of *multilevel governance as dispersion of state authority*. Originally elaborated in the context of theories of European integration, this definition of multilevel governance has underpinned following theorisations on the redefinition of state sovereignty and power rescaling, leading to what Alcantara and Nelles (2014; see also: Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016) call the *system(s) approach* to multilevel governance. In this perspective, multilevel governance is understood as “an all-encompassing phenomenon that manifests itself in various forms,” (Alcantara, Broschek and Nelles 2016, p. 5), like for instance Hooghe and Marks (2001 and 2003) sub-type I (reflecting federal systems) and sub-type II multilevel governance.

The generic and the systems’ definition of multilevel governance, while very influential in debates in theorisations on the changing nature of the nation-state and processes of EU integration (see e.g., Stephenson 2013), focus on the analysis of macro-processes and structures that do not help to account for the specific modes that policymaking and governance may take when faced with conditions of turbulence and crisis.

To this end, the specific and *operational definition of multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking* appears more promising. Following this approach, multilevel governance is defined by *three key and distinctive features: 1) different levels of government are simultaneously involved; 2)*

³ https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/urban-rural-and-regional-development/oecd-multi-level-governance-studies_2414679x.

non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved; 3) relationships defy existing hierarchies and take the form of non-hierarchical networks. The instance approach to multilevel governance characterises as intrinsically relational and meso-level, since it draws attention to the multiple relations – between governmental actors at different territorial levels and between public and non-public actors – that take place in order to face specific policy issues. Interactivity and interdependence can be regarded as the very hallmarks of multilevel governance modes of policymaking, whereby “decision-making is negotiated and shared between actors in large part because none of the participants possesses the authority or the capacity to undertake the issue alone” (Alcantara, Broschek and Nelles 2016, 8). *From the robust governance theoretical perspective, the question arises of how interactivity in multilevel governance arrangements can be mobilised in times of turbulence to contribute new ideas, resources and innovative strategies to the shaping of robust responses to crisis.*

Our literature review also identifies a *second operational definition* of multilevel governance as *coordination arrangements between national, regional and local governments, as well as across jurisdictions*, that characterises policy-experts debates and more specifically the work of the Multilevel Governance and Decentralization unit of OECD. The emphasis on coordination – rather than collaboration – and the limited focus on public authorities, reflects a primary interest of OECD for intergovernmental relations. However, in the perspective of robust governance theory, this might sound as a too limited approach to interactivity, since it overlooks the multiplicity of stakeholders whose resources might reveal crucial in order to advance innovative and flexible in face of mounting crises.

Hence, the instance approach to multilevel governance and its operational definition emphasizing relationships across different levels of government and among different types of actors, appears as the more promising in terms of contribution to the theorization of robust governance in times of turbulence, as we will discuss below in section 4.

3. Multilevel Governance in the literature on emergency response policies

In this section we delve deeper into the literature dealing with emergency response policies in order to understand how multilevel governance has been understood and analysed in this more specific research stream. In general, if there is no doubt that multilevel governance, both in its vertical and horizontal dimension, is considered a key feature enabling coordination in systems of emergency intervention in European countries and beyond, still there are differences in how intergovernmental relations and public-non-public actors' relations are concretely organised and carried out, as we shall see below. Furthermore, whereas some studies clearly focus on intergovernmental coordination, and therefore on vertical multilevel governance relations, others concentrate on multi-agency collaboration and on horizontal relations between public institutions and non-public actors.

3.1 Emergency response policy: what is it and why multilevel governance is important

An emergency policy is composed of four main intervention categories: mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. In practice, all these policies overlap to a certain extent, but they also differ in some respects. Mitigation and preparedness policies are in general antecedent to a turbulence. The focus of mitigation policies is ‘to prevent hazards from developing into complete disasters or to reduce the effects of disasters when they occur’ (Chu 2011, 451). Some examples of such policies are: creating channels for volcanic debris flows, building dams, riverbanks, or wildfire corridors.

Preparedness policies are composed of measures that are aimed at preparing people and organizations to react to hazardous events promptly, by forecasting the probability of future risky events and by recognizing alarming situations before the turbulence occurs (Handmer and Dovers, 2007; Fischbacher-Smith and Fischbacher-Smith 2016). Some examples of preparedness policies are training programs for emergency managers and drills.

By contrast, emergency response policies take place while the shock or crisis is happening and immediately after, and they are aimed at reducing damage, avoiding disasters or catastrophes and at securing (at least partially) the provision of services and public goods (Schneider, 2011). Early evacuations, rescue operations and the special purchase and distribution of goods are all examples of these policies. Recovery policies usually take place after the severest phase of the emergency has been overcome (Kendra and Wachtendorf, 2003; Haddow *et al.*, 2007), and are put in place in order to recover from the consequences and ripple effects of a turbulence and to build a new normality, possibly avoiding reproducing past vulnerabilities and trying to take a step forward toward the mitigation of future disasters (Arendt and Alesh, 2015). The reconstruction of streets and buildings after earthquakes or hurricanes and support for the renewal of social and economic activities are some examples of this latter type of emergency policy.

Response policies are the most challenging and stressful type of emergency policies (Handmer and Dovers, 2007; Ross, 2014). The lack of time, which may also characterize many policies in normal periods, becomes dramatic under such conditions (Arendt and Alesh 2015, 189; Kapucu and Boin, 2016), and any change in the problem and/or situation, which is always possible in contexts of turbulence, becomes sudden and pervasive (Clarke, 1999; Handmer and Dovers, 2007). Finally, response policies are more likely to fall under the mass media spotlight than mitigation, preparedness and recovery policies (Schneider 2011), thereby increasing the pressure and stress for the people involved in the emergency management activities.

The *emergency management model* of most countries is set according to the so-called *Incident Management System (IMS)*. The IMS is centred on *two main pillars: 1) an integrated multilevel governance system, that requires strong engagement and collaboration of all government levels and of public and private actors; 2) the application of emergency management plans that tell operators how to act in the face of specific situations* (Waugh 2000; Kapucu 2008; Somers and Svara 2009; Schneider 2011; Fagel 2014; Johnson and Mamula-Seadon 2014; Arendt and Alesh 2015; Fischbacher-Smith and Fischbacher-Smith 2016; Robinson *et al.* 2016; Vasavada 2016; Sylves 2020).

Hence, to this day, multilevel governance remains a fundamental aspect of emergency response policies, both in its vertical dimension, that pertains to intergovernmental relations, and in its horizontal dimension, that pertains to the collaboration between public and private actors (Sylves 2020).

3.2 Intergovernmental relationships. Top-down and bottom-up modes of coordination

As far as intergovernmental relationships are concerned, the literature on emergency management distinguishes between bottom-up and top-down modes of coordination.

In bottom-up multilevel governance systems, lower-level governments are firstly required to create local emergency preparedness agencies. These agencies should prepare emergency management plans that define duties and responsibilities for offices and personnel and offer clear guidelines on procedures (evacuation or quarantine protocols, warning and communication procedures, inter-municipal arrangements, mutual aid and funding rules etc.). Secondly, intermediate-level governments

(states, regions) are required to prepare national emergency management plans that give clear guidelines on when and how to mobilize national corps and on the criteria to distribute resources among stricken local territories (Miccoli and Destefano 2010; Van Eeten *et al.* 2011; Fischbacher-Smith and Fischbacher-Smith 2016). When a crisis or a disaster happens, local governments are expected to act quickly following their emergency management plans, while state (or regional) governments are expected to act as the main connecting hubs between local governments and the federal (or national) government and to provide aid to local governments if explicitly and officially requested by them. Central governments are expected to set the main conditions that lower-level governments have to respect in order to obtain financial resources and technical aid. Requests from local and regional governments take the form of formal reports documenting the extent of damage, the level of need, and the type of help needed. National or federal intervention is then implemented *through*, not *in place of*, lower-level governments.

Today, many countries, especially federal countries and highly decentralized states, have officially established a type of bottom-up multilevel governance system, whereas in the past IMS was predominantly focused on the command-and-control approach, centered on a 'military-style' organizational culture (Waugh 1993, 2000; Waugh and Streib 2006; Somers and Svara 2009; Schneider 2011; Kapuku and Boin, 2016; O'Donovan 2019). A typical example of the bottom-up model is the US IMS. When American communities are stricken by natural or human disasters, local governments must respond and take care of relief and reconstruction in cooperation with private for-profit and non-profit organizations. If they need support from upper-level governments, local governments have to embark on a codified procedure and the same must be done by the states.

In other words, in case of emergency, local governments have to follow the conditions for assistance that they have been previously signed with their state government and, at their turn, State governments follow the conditions for assistance that they have previously signed with the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) through a specific FEMA-State Agreement. This is a "legal document between FEMA and the affected state that describes the understandings, commitments, and binding conditions for assistance applicable as the result of the major disaster or emergency declared by the President" (Sylves 2020, 223). Hence, to formally request state or federal intervention, local and state emergency agencies must prepare detailed reports on damages, costs and personnel needs. Typically, this procedure implies the filling out of lots of documents, to be sent, respectively, to the State Emergency Management Agency when the emergency is local, to FEMA in case of major disasters. FEMA, together with the federal Department of Homeland Security (DHS), established after the 9/11 terrorist attack, is responsible for the coordination of all emergency management operations on the federal territory. The FEMA staff analyses the dossiers and brings its evaluation before the American President, who has the last say on the matter and decides whether to grant financial and human resources or not. In the case of a positive decision, the President makes an official declaration of 'major disaster', specifying the boundaries of the area that deserves the federal aid and the types and amount of aid (but usually no more than 75% of the total requested funds), and nominates a Federal Coordinating Officer (FCO) as representative of the President in the affected area (Waugh 2000; O'Donovan 2019). FEMA then prepares and signs a Memorandum of Understanding with each emergency management agency of the states affected by the disaster, to establish the environmental and historic preservation priorities, the interagency communication protocols, periodic meetings, the personnel at disposal and the protocols to share data and information (Sylves 2020).

United Kingdom and New Zealand share a similar system, with local agencies responsible for the emergency operations, and local and national (regional for the New Zealand) governments applying for the Emergency response and recovery scheme at the central level (Schneider 2011).

In top-down multilevel governance systems, the central State takes control of both strategic choices and operative processes, often in collaboration with private organizations and private actors. Lower governments intervene to complement and facilitate operations (Britton 2007). This system usually provides for the mobilization of special corps, like national guards and the army. India and Philippines multilevel governance systems in emergency situations verge on this model, but it has also been applied exceptionally in the US after the collapse of the twin towers on September 11, 2001 (Schneider 2011).

An extreme example of the top-down model is the one introduced by Israel when the government had to cope with the sudden waves of migration it experienced over the decades. Two in particular were the critical moments: the years immediately following the independence of the state of Israel, achieved in 1948 (1949-1952), and the years immediately following the collapse of the communist regime in the USSR and the opening of the Russian borders (1990-1994). In both critical phases, the government of Israel intervened directly to boost the existing housing stock (Sharkansky and Zalmanovitch 2000). In 1990 in particular, the Israeli government and parliament intervened with an unprecedented housing expansion plan. In June 1990, the Knesset passed the Planning and Building Procedures Interim Law. The law stipulated that housing proposals comprising 200 or more units could be brought directly before one of six new District Housing Commissions (DHC), without prior approval at the local level, as it was normally required. These DHCs were entitled to change existing land-use regulations, grant building contracts, and authorize building plans. The law limited the provisions regarding citizen participation, the priority of national and regional plans, and possibilities of appeal. In essence, the national government centralized and drastically reduced approval and control procedures, even introducing procedural anomalies, such as permits given retroactively, public assignments without competition or even without contracts. The scarcity of resources (money, cement, building materials) was faced with exceptional measures like donations from Jews abroad and especially loan guarantees from the United States. Lands that had been set aside for local parks and water reserves were used to locate the new buildings and local public land was sold substantially below market price. Some of the contractors who were hired had no experience in residential constructions and some lacked adequate financing and soon went insolvent, but the State intervened directly in all situations to guarantee the construction of the houses.

Both bottom-up and top-down multilevel models frequently resort to emphasize complementary intergovernmental relations, like military aids for rescue operations, transport equipment and logistics and mutual aid between same-level jurisdictions (Sylves 2020). For example, China has introduced a system called 'paired assistance policy' (PAP) to earthquake disaster management (Zhang and Tang 2021). It consists in the central State matching each stricken city or province with another city or province that is 'economically prosperous' but not affected by the earthquake, and that is assigned the task to coordinate emergency intervention in the city/province affected by the earthquake. Once the cities and provinces responsible for response and recovery actions have been identified, the central State sets the minimum amount of economic resources they are required to invest, gives guidelines about the tasks they have to carry out to aid the paired cities or provinces, and coordinate the operations (Zhang and Tang 2021, 141). PAP was applied to respond to the Wenchuan earthquake (2008) and to the Lushan earthquake (2013): tens of economically prosperous cities and provinces were chosen by the central State managers and these cities, coordinated by State officials, assisted the affected areas by sending funds, contributing to the reconstruction of communication and industrial infrastructures, and helping local officials to work in extreme conditions, like school teachers or nurses (Zhang and Tang 2021). Similarly, in the United States, the Emergency Management Assistance Compact (EMAC) provides for states-to-state mutual aid: when a state is affected by a disaster, its national EMAC Authorized Representative opens an event in the online EMAC Operation

System, then the state emergency management agency forwards resources requests to the EMAC team, which contact states to fulfil the request, beginning from the closest ones in terms of travel/time distance. The assisting states have to activate their in-state EMAC protocols and communicate what they are able to provide. Before the mutual-aid operations start, the requesting states and the assisting states complete the EMAC Request for Assistance Form (REQ-A), which constitutes a legally binding agreement between them. Managers and personnel deployed by the assisting states must track all mission expenses and documentation and maintain contacts with their state emergency management agency, because all this information is necessary to obtain EMAC reimbursement. The same tracking and reporting is due by the assisted states, because they must contribute to the reimbursement in case they also receive federal disaster assistance funding. In these efforts, also personnel from the affected local governments contribute to collect and report information (Sylves 2020).

The bottom-up governance mode is generally considered more capable to foster robust emergency operations, because it allows for more flexibility in dealing with the unpredictability of the emergency situation (Waugh, 2000; Wise 2006; Schneider, 2011), although top-down interventions are considered necessary when lower-level governments enter in competition and act strategically to enlist central-level resources (Quarantelli 2006; Wise 2006; Moynihan 2009; Sapountzaki and Papachatzki 2011; Schneider 2011).

However, several empirical studies have shown that all multilevel governance systems in emergency situations, even those systems that are designed accurately, suffer of some degree of confusion, problems of coordination, and ambiguities in the roles and responsibilities of the various involved actors (Wolensky and Wolensky 1990; Quarantelli 2006; Birkland 2009; Comfort and Kapuku 2009; Kapuku 2009; Moynihan 2009; Ansell *et al.* 2010; McGuire and Agranoff 2011; Sapountzaki and Papachatzki 2011; Schneider 2011). As a consequence, central governments often end up intervening directly and in place of lower-level governments to deal with the disfunctions of bottom-up multilevel governance systems and vice-versa (Birkland 2009a; Comfort and Kapuku 2009; Kapuku 2009; Somers and Svava 2009; Ansell *et al.* 2010; McGuire and Agranoff 2011; Christensen and Laegreid 2020).

3.3 The horizontal dimension. Multi-agency collaboration

Private organizations, profit and non-profit, are involved in emergency response efforts in order to integrate public resources with private contributions, to include complementary perspectives and expertise and to enable more capillary interactions with the population (Sylves 2020). Private organizations, such as private firms or non-profit associations, integrate public resources with money or in-kind donations and through the provision of their personnel to help civil servants and public managers. For example, in the response to the disaster caused by hurricane Katrina, Walmart played a key role shoulder to shoulder with public institutions and NGOs: the company donated \$17 million to relief NGOs and the Red Cross and \$3 million worth of goods to shelters for people and animals, organized truck deliveries containing supplies, clothes and computers, and initiated the first online 'Emergency contact service' campaign, through which people affected by the hurricane could contact their family and friends (Horowitz 2009). Experts and specialists are often involved in emergency operations through advisory boards and scientific or multi-stakeholder committees to advise governments and parliaments about critical decisions and operative problems (Moore and Lakha 2011). NGOs, associations and grassroots groups are usually involved in first-aid services, like food distribution, child care services, medical care, home repair and debris removal through their trained personnel and untrained but instrumental helpers (Medury 2011; O'Donovan 2019; Sylves 2020). For example, in Hong Kong, at the beginning of the COVID-19 emergency, when there was no

government provision of personal protection equipment and the prices on the market were rising, grassroots activists began to import facemasks and distribute them free of charge to underprivileged residents (Hartley and Jarvis 2020).

Some countries even encourage the development of so-called 'community emergency response' teams through training national programs on emergency operations. Individuals who aim at being part of these teams must attend training programs and earn specific qualifications for various types of disaster management operations. They offer their work voluntarily when a disaster happens and come back to their lives when the assigned tasks have been carried out (Sylvès 2020).

The sudden activation of all these organizations and people, which is called 'convergence behavior', is a valuable resource but, at the same time, it also represents two serious problems. The first is that government emergency management officials can never be sure how much help voluntary organizations and groups are able to provide (Sylvès 2020). The second is a problem of *difficulty in coordinating all these emergent organizations, with the consequent risk of diverting part of the efforts from the management of the emergency to the management of public-private interactions* (Waugh 2000). Add to this the problem of the so-called 'milling process' (Turner and Killian 1987), through which citizens, who find themselves having to respond to an emergency situation in the absence of or not knowing precise courses of action for that specific situation, try to address emerging needs informally and spontaneously (Tierney, Lindell and Perry 2001; McEntire 2007). To facilitate the management of these problems, in some countries umbrella groups have been created, to serve as forums in which voluntary organizations, associations and NGOs share knowledge and resources throughout the disaster cycle and avoid unnecessary duplication of efforts (Sylvès 2020).

3.4 Facilitating the coordination of organizations and processes

Coordinating hundreds of organizations and thousands of operators is considered one of the most difficult challenges of emergency response processes. To facilitate coordination, some strategies and arrangements are usually applied by central and lower-level governments. *Ad hoc* upper-level teams (federal or national) are often created similarly to the 'control rooms' that operate in so called High-Reliability Organizations (HRO), namely those organizations that have the task of managing hazardous systems like nuclear plants, air traffic control centres, space agencies etc. (Boin and Fishbacher-Smith 2011; Boin and Van Eeten 2016). These teams are composed of people who have different expertise and operative responsibilities in public agencies (Robinson *et al.* 2016; Vasavada 2016). Central governments assign them temporary and extraordinary powers, in order to let them act with wide room for manoeuvre to establish the main operative priorities, like where and how to procure and distribute equipment, supplies, and personnel (Lundberg 2009). In order to coordinate and steer promptly and flexibly, these teams set up frequent (formal and informal) meetings with the public and private organizations involved in the management of the emergency at different levels (Arendt and Alesh 2015) and collect information on different policy processes and on the underlying motivations of policy makers. As a consequence, they are able to intervene rapidly in case of conflicts or stalemates among lower-level governments and between public and private actors involved in response operations (Waugh 2000; Arendt and Alesh 2015). Sometimes, even lower-level governments create this kind of teams with similar tasks applied to subnational territories (Arendt and Alesh 2015).

A typical example of central multi-expertise teams are the federal disaster response task forces created since 1989 by FEMA in the United States. These task forces can be deployed to assist and coordinate state and local governments when a major disaster happens. Members of these task forces are usually trained and experts in different fields in relation to the specificity of the disaster: specific

technical expertise in fields like engineering, physics, medicine etc., managerial skills pertaining logistics, planning etc., and experts in administrative procedures and tools (Sylves 2020).

Complementary to these teams, sometimes central governments dispatch a representative to the staff of each state emergency agency, so that the chain of command, communication and coordination can be efficiently shortened (Sylves 2020).

The literature has also highlighted some factors that seem to foster a smoother coordination between jurisdictions at different levels and between public and private actors, i.e.:

- Good and consolidated working relationships between state or region governors and directors of territorial sections of the federal or national emergency agency (Sylves 2020)
- Fresh experience in major disasters (McGuire and Silvia 2010), effective training programs and emergency agencies with multiple functional areas (McGuire and Silvia 2010).

4. Multilevel governance and robustness. A complicated the nexus

The literature reviewed above clearly shows how the concept of multilevel governance, while originally introduced to signify processes of redefinition of state authority and national sovereignty in Europe, in the course of the last two decades has acquired a crucial relevance in debates on policymaking and governance, as well as in the more specific literature on responses to emergency. The definition of multilevel governance as a specific instance or mode of policymaking characterized by intense and collaborative interactions between *at the same time* authorities at different levels of government and public and non-public actors, has prompted a new attention for interactivity in multilevel policymaking arrangements, beyond formal structures of allocation of competences and responsibility. In other words, a key research question in the instance approach to multilevel governance is:

How and to what extent can interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking arrangements favor more effective and more legitimate policy responses in times of heightened turbulence?

This question brings to the fore the debate on the potential trade-offs in multilevel governance policymaking between problem-solving capacity and democratic accountability (Papadopoulos 2007 and 2010; Maggetti and Trein 2019), which is certainly crucial in the robust governance perspective, that aims “to effectively solve emerging problems and challenges while ensuring broad-based support to the changing solutions as well as to the overall system of governance” (Deliverable 2.1, p. 39). Papadopoulos (2010) identifies four properties of multilevel governance that can produce a democratic accountability deficit: 1) a lack of visibility of governance networks, which deliberately operate informally and opaquely in order to facilitate compromise; 2) uncoupling from representative institutions, in the sense that decisions prepared and implemented by networks lead a weakening of the legislative and control functions of parliaments; 3) the composition of networks, which does not necessarily reflect all possible relevant social interests but only those that are able to organise in powerful organisations listened to by decision-makers; and 4) the multilevelness itself, which creates a double accountability dilemma for policymakers – to electoral constituencies on the one hand and to partners in specific multilevel governance venues on the other.

As is clear, this critique, while alerting us on the possible pitfalls of multilevel governance, does not seem to reflect on how interactivity within these arrangements does concretely take place. In other words, as shown by the empirical research reviewed above, multilevel governance policymaking may involve very different configurations: it can be promoted top-down by central (national/EU) authorities or bottom-up by regional/local institutions, it can include different types of non-public actors, and can imply more or less formal/informal relationships. All these features have to be considered when assessing the possible trade-offs of multilevel governance as a problem-solving strategy.

The goal of this Report is precisely that of identifying possible configurations or varieties of interactivity in multilevel governance that can potentially contribute to the robust governance of crises by ensuring at the same time that efficient solutions are pursued and principles of democratic legitimacy and accountability are fulfilled.

To this end, sections 5 and 6 are devoted to the elaboration of a theoretical framework aimed at deepening our understanding of the of the nexus between multilevel governance and robust response to crises in times of heightened turbulence. In section 5 below, we identify and operationalize four key dimensions of interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking and, on this basis, we build a typology of configurations or variants of multilevel governance. Hence, in section 6, we present our hypotheses on how different configurations can contribute to the robust governance of turbulence and of the crises that come with it.

5. Dimension of multilevel governance and typology

Taking stock of the literature review carried out above, in this section we single out four key dimensions of interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking and operationalize them through critical questions that reflect the objectives of this Report, i.e., to elucidate the possible configurations of multilevel governance policymaking that can contribute to the robust governance of turbulence, as showed in Table 4.1 below.

TABLE 4.1 - DIMENSIONS OF MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE (MLG) POLICYMAKING AND CRITICAL QUESTIONS

Dimension	Critical questions	Possible answers	
1) Stage of policymaking	At what stage of the policy process is/was MLG interactivity taking place?	Decision-making	Implementation
2) Initiative and Leadership	Who/which institution/organization took the initiative to convene the MLG venue/arrangement?	Top-down	Bottom-up
3) Actors of interactivity	Who takes/took part in the MLG venue/arrangement?	Primarily Vertical	Prim. Horizontal

4) Mode of interaction	How is/was interactivity in the MLG venue/arrangement taking place?	High Formality	Informality
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1. Stage of policymaking

The first dimension regards whether the multilevel governance arrangement has been established to operate in support of *decision-making processes* or rather in the *implementation* of specific measures (e.g., vaccination programme in a specific region/area). This distinction is a key one, since it enables to identify possible differences in terms of formal leadership of multilevel governance policymaking, actors engaged and level of institutionalisation. More specifically, we can expect that whereas multilevel governance in decision-making processes will often take a highly structured form, with a clear leadership, the participation of key stakeholders and a relatively high level of institutionalisation, in implementation processes we can find more fluid arrangements, where different actors and organizations can contribute to put in place specific measures often also through informal relations.

However, the distinction between the two stages can be unclear, since multilevel governance policy venues can sometimes operate at both levels. At which stage of the policymaking process does an arrangement concretely operate is therefore an empirical question.

2. Initiative and leadership

The second dimension of multilevel governance interactivity aims at highlighting whether the specific arrangement has been established **top-down** by EU institutions and/or national governments or whether it has been started **bottom-up**, as a result of the pressure or formal requests put forward by local governments and non-governmental organisations on higher levels of government. In other terms, the objective is to understand which institution/organisation/actor has taken leadership in establishing the specific multilevel governance venue or process. This requests the in-depth reconstruction of the policy process and more specifically of how it came into being, since formal leadership as reported by official documents might not reflect the factual reality of who took the initiative in the first place and promoted the creation of the venue (see above 2.3). Furthermore, the initial promoters are likely to keep a key role of leaders throughout the process, even though this is formally assigned to other institutional actors.

3. Type of actors involved

As pointed out by our literature review above (see in particular 2.3), multilevel governance arrangements can have a very diverse composition in terms of type of participants. Whereas some venues primarily engage governmental actors and only few representatives of non-public stakeholders, therefore reflecting primarily the vertical/intergovernmental dimension of multilevel governance, others can include a broader range of non-governmental actors on the horizontal dimension. We can expect that the prevalence of either type of actors will influence multilevel governance interactivity, which is likely to be more hierarchical when the vertical dimension prevails, and more cooperative when there is a wide participation of non-public actors. Again,

empirical research is fundamental in order to assess how interactivity changes according to type of prevalent actors engaged in the multilevel governance arrangement.

4. Level of institutionalization and mode of interaction

This dimension clearly links to the previous one on the prevailing type of actors in multilevel governance policymaking arrangements. In fact, when the vertical dimension prevails, we can also expect more formalized and institutionalised interactions (in terms e.g., of procedures, membership, regularity of meetings etc.), whereas the inclusion of multiple non-public stakeholders is likely to favour more flexible and informal interactions. However, the correspondence between the two dimensions should not be taken for granted. Multilevel governance arrangements, even when participants are primarily governmental authorities, can still be still characterised by a high level of informality, especially at international or EU level, where hierarchical relations are less relevant, as highlighted by the frequent and informal interactions between the European Commission and local authorities on various matters (see e.g., Piattoni 2010 on social cohesion and environmental issues; Caponio 2022b on migration). At the same time, the participation of a wide range of different non-governmental actors in multilevel governance decision-making venues might require some degree of formalisation of policy relevant interactions.

Hence, considering the preliminary distinction between multilevel governance in decision-making and implementation, the three other dimensions can assume in principle two opposed values, each one reflecting a specific mode of interactivity, i.e., top-down vs bottom-up, vertical vs horizontal, and formal vs informal (see table 4.1). The combination of these six values or properties of interactivity lead to the identification of 16 configurations or variants of interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking, 8 for each stage of the policy process, as shown by table 4.2 below.

TABLE 4. 2 - CONFIGURATIONS OR VARIANTS OF MLG

Decision-making	Implementation
1) Top-down, primarily vertical actors, prevailing formality – Centralised MLG	9) Top-down, primarily vertical actors, prevailing formality – Centralised MLG
2) Top-down, primarily vertical actors, high informality	10) Top-down, primarily vertical actors, high informality
3) Top-down, primarily horizontal actors, high formality	11) Top-down, primarily horizontal actors, high formality
4) Top-down, primarily horizontal actors, high informality	12) Top-down, primarily horizontal actors, high informality
5) Bottom-up, primarily vertical actors, high formality	13) Bottom-up, primarily vertical actors, high formality

6) Bottom-up, primarily vertical actors, high informality	14) Bottom-up, primarily vertical actors, high informality
7) Bottom-up, primarily horizontal actors, high formality	15) Bottom-up, primarily horizontal actors, high formality
8) Bottom-up, primarily horizontal actors, high informality – Decentralised MLG	16) Bottom-up, primarily horizontal actors, high informality – Decentralised MLG

Having identified 16 varieties of multilevel governance policymaking, in the section below we illustrate more in-depth the two opposite ideal-type configurations of centralized and decentralized multilevel governance and discuss our hypotheses in terms of contribution of these two configurations to the robust governance of turbulence and of the crises that come with it.

6. Hypotheses. Multilevel governance and robust responses to crisis

The configurational analysis carried out above enable us to identify two opposed ideal-types of multilevel governance policymaking, i.e., centralised and decentralised multilevel governance, each characterised by a different combination of the properties on dimensions 2, 3 and 4. On this basis, we can formulate theoretical expectations/hypotheses in terms of the contribution of the two multilevel governance ideal-types to the robust governance of crises.

1. Centralised multilevel governance (configurations 1 & 9)

The centralised ideal-type of multilevel governance policymaking reflects configuration 1 in decision-making processes and configuration 9 in policy implementation. This variant is characterised by: i) a top-down initiative and leadership, in the sense that the multilevel governance arrangement is launched and led by a governmental institution/agency (e.g., international institution, national government, regional/local executive), that plays a central role in its organisation and concrete functioning; ii) a composition skewed toward the representatives of different governmental authorities, with the participation of a limited number of atypical/key stakeholders (depending on the issue, non-governmental organizations, private companies etc.); iii) a high level of formalisation of actors' interactions and relations.

As a result of this combination, we can expect a pattern of prevalently hierarchical and formalized interactivity. This may enable effective decision taking, because of the highly centralised leadership ensured by public authorities, yet at the expenses of democratic accountability. In fact, interaction with stakeholders and non-state actors is likely to be limited to those organisations that are 'known' by the institution leading the initiative and/or share its same views, therefore limiting the range of interests and perspectives participating in the definition of possible courses of action and policy responses.

Hence, in terms of contribution to the robust governance of crises, the centralised ideal-type appears as rather dysfunctional. First of all, the top-down selection of a limited number of stakeholders, constraints the range of policy options to the routine modes of intervention preferred by public authorities, eventually impeding the consideration of innovative solutions put forward by the wider range of non-public actors excluded from the policymaking venue. Furthermore, the highly formalized and rather hierarchical mode of interaction does not allow for the flexibility and adaptive mindset that is requested to public policymakers in times of crises (see Deliverable D2.1). Centralised multilevel governance, not only does not ensure the deploying of those adaptive and flexible strategies that help to effectively solve new problems and challenges, but may even impede the emergence of innovative solutions. With respect to legitimacy, centralized multilevel governance shows certainly a high level of procedural legitimacy since the policymaking arrangement is endowed with the power deriving from the electoral procedure, yet it lacks process legitimacy because of the limited number of stakeholders allowed to participate (for the distinction between procedural and process problem-solving see: Trein, Thomann and Maggetti 2019).

An extreme example of *centralized multilevel governance* arrangement is a governmental Emergency Task Forces set up to undertake key decisions in face of the turbulence caused by a crisis like the spread of the Covid pandemic or the mass arrival of asylum seekers from areas of war. Table 4.3 illustrates the key characteristics of this type of arrangement on the three dimensions of multilevel governance analysed above, and provides an assessment of its – hypothetical – contribution to robust crisis governance in terms of innovation, adaptation/flexibility and legitimacy.

TABLE 4.3 - HYPOTHETICAL CENTRALISED MLG ARRANGEMENT. CONTRIBUTION TO THE ROBUST GOVERNANCE OF CRISES

	Innovation	Adaptation/Flexibility	Legitimacy
<p>Governmental emergency task force:</p> <p>1) Established by the prime minister; 2) heads of key Ministries, key public agencies or local/regional governments, main health services contractors (private companies and/or NGOs); 3) highly formalized and hierarchical relations</p>	<p>Limited:</p> <p>Few 'like-minded' actors prioritizing quick fixes and status-quo</p>	<p>Constrained by the formality of the relations among the participants</p>	<p>High procedural legitimacy (government electoral mandate), low process legitimacy (few stakeholders involved)</p>

The in-depth analysis of concrete cases of multilevel governance arrangements and their nexus with the robust governance of turbulence is a central objective of the Robust project and will be carried out in Deliverable 3.2, *Comparative analysis of multilevel governance during crisis*.

2. Decentralised multilevel governance (Configurations 8 & 16)

The decentralised ideal-type of multilevel governance policymaking is represented by configuration 8 in decision-making processes and 16 in policy implementation. This configuration shows properties that are diametrically opposed to those characterising the centralised ideal-type: i) the multilevel governance arrangement is established bottom-up, because of the efforts of leaders in local administrations and/or grass-roots communities or non-public organizations; ii) it is open to the participation of a large pool of public and non-public actors, representing different interests and points of view on the issues at stake, and contributing different resources for possible solutions; iii) the structure is flexible and underpinned by both formal and informal interactions and relationships.

In the decentralized ideal-type of multilevel policymaking, interactivity is likely to take the form of collaborative, peer-to-peer and often informal relations, which will strengthen democratic accountability and legitimacy. However, the potentially high number of actors involved and the prevailing informality of their relations, implying also some volatility in terms of commitment and engagement in the policymaking venue, is likely to affect negatively decision-taking capacity.

In terms of contribution to the robust governance of crises, the decentralised ideal-type of multilevel governance appears more promising than the centralised one. Bottom-up leadership, the inclusion of a greater number of stakeholders and collaborative informal relations are potential resources that can favour flexible adaptation and innovative thinking while at the same time reinforcing trust in the policy process and support for the institutions and organizations involved.

An extreme example of *decentralized multilevel governance* arrangement is a consultative Roundtable or Platform mobilized by local communities' leaders (e.g., mayors or NGOs leaders) to influence key decisions in face of the turbulence caused by a crisis like the spread of the Covid pandemic or the mass arrival of asylum seekers from areas of war. Table 4.4 illustrates the key characteristics of this type of arrangement on the three dimensions of multilevel governance analysed above, and provides an assessment of its – hypothetical – contribution to robust crisis governance in terms of innovation, adaptation/flexibility and legitimacy.

TABLE 4.4 - HYPOTHETICAL CASE OF DECENTRALISED MLG. CONTRIBUTION TO THE ROBUST GOVERNANCE OF CRISES

	Innovation	Adaptation/Flexibility	Legitimacy
Consultative Roundtable: 1) mobilised bottom-up by grassroots leaders; 2) open to the participation of multiple stakeholders; 3) high level of informal relations based on trust.	Potentially high: mobilisation of different ideas and resources in the affected local communities	Favoured by informality and trust relations	High level of process legitimacy but lower procedural legitimacy (the venue is not convened by an elected government)

The decentralised multilevel governance clearly reflects a configuration of policymaking taking place at a local level, where public and non-public actors typically operating at different governance levels interact on specific issues and challenges (Caponio 2023). The analysis of concrete cases of multilevel governance arrangements and their contribution to the robust governance of crisis is a central objective of the Robust project and will be carried out in Deliverable 3.2, *Comparative analysis of multilevel governance during crisis*.

Hence, building on our conceptualization of variants of multilevel governance, we can tentatively put forward the following theoretical expectations or hypotheses on the impact of multilevel governance on robustness:

The more multilevel governance arrangements are decentralized, presenting a mode of interactivity based on trust, cooperation and informality, the more they will contribute to the emergence of robust solutions in response to crises.

In a symmetric manner, we should expect that

The more multilevel governance arrangements are centralized, presenting a mode of interactivity showing hierarchy, control and formality, the less they will contribute to the emergence of robust solutions in response to crises.

However, as highlighted in the review of the literature on emergency response policy, especially when facing situations of heightened crisis, top-down leadership can to some extent favour coordination and collaboration, which can strengthen efficient responses in emergency relief (see e.g., the 'Paired assistance policy' – PAP in China or Emergency Management Assistance Compact - EMAC). At the same time, the identification of a limited number of key stakeholders can enhance decision-making capacity, while a minimum level of formalisation of actors' membership and engagement can favour the stability of the policymaking arrangement. Hence, beyond the hypothetical multilevel governance arrangements presented in table 4.3 and 4.4, we can expect to find a multiplicity of concrete multilevel policymaking processes showing a mix of different combination of the properties on dimensions 2 (initiative and leadership), 3 (type of participants) and 4 (level of institutionalisation and mode of interaction).

The puzzle then becomes that of understanding *which varieties of multilevel governance (see table 4.2) are likely to be more conducive to the robust governance of crises in different situations and contexts and why.*

This is precisely the objective of WP3 second Report (D3.2), that will analyse concrete cases of robust and less robust responses to turbulence in the context of the economic, refugee and Covid-19 crisis in the Robust Consortium partner countries, in order to identify the possible variants of multilevel governance favouring the emergence of robust governance.

Conclusion

Multilevel governance is not only a highly debated notion in different streams of scholarly literature in political science, sociology and (critical) political geography, to name just a few, but also a normative idea, underlying discussions in various – local, regional, EU – policymaking circles and fora. From the normative point of view, the ambition is that of offering an alternative paradigm to hierarchical policymaking, by substituting command and control with collaboration and coordination across different levels of government and among all concerned public and non-public actors (Piattoni 2010). In this perspective, multilevel governance can represent a key strategy to achieve robust crisis governance, implying at the same time the capacity to alleviate turbulence without compromising democracy, but rather reinforcing its core values and norms (see Deliverable D2.1 – Proof of Concept).

In order to better figure out the possible relations between multilevel governance and robustness, in this Report we have first clarified the different definitions and uses of multilevel governance that can be found in the literature and in policy-oriented debates. Of a particular relevance in this perspective appears the *instance approach to multilevel governance*, since it brings to the fore the multiplicity of actors that, at different levels, take part, with their ideas and resources, to policymaking processes on specific issues. Following this approach, multilevel governance can be defined as an arrangement or processes that presents three key features: *1) different levels of government are simultaneously involved; 2) non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved; 3) relationships defy existing hierarchies and take the form of non-hierarchical networks.*

This definition of multilevel governance seems also to underlie the more specific research on emergency response policies, that looks at both vertical and horizontal relations in multilevel governance as fundamental to enable smooth coordination in systems of emergency intervention. It follows that an instance approach to multilevel governance appears as the most promising in terms of contribution to the theorisation of robust governance in times of turbulence.

Hence, the second part of the Report has been devoted precisely to the building of a theoretical framework aimed at pushing forward our understanding of how and to what extent *interactivity in MLG policymaking arrangements can favour the emergence of effective and legitimate policy responses to turbulence and therefore, of a robust governance of crises.* To this end, we have singled out four key dimensions of interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking, i.e.: 1) stage of policymaking; 2) initiative and leadership; 3) type of actors involved; 4) level of institutionalization and mode of interaction. The combination of the six values or properties of interactivity assumed by dimensions n. 2, 3 and 4 has led to the identification of 8 configurations or variants of multilevel governance interactivity in decision-making and 8 in implementation processes, as well as of 2 ideal-type configurations: *centralized and decentralized multilevel governance.*

Building on these premises, we have hypothesised that, whereas centralized multilevel governance presents a mode of interactivity underpinned by hierarchy, control and formality, and therefore lacks the kind of propensity to adaptation and flexibility that is necessary for the emergence of robust solutions in response to crises, decentralised governance represents a more favourable configuration for robust governance, since interactivity in this case is based on trust, cooperation and informality. However, intermediate variants are also possible: which specific configurations can favour the emergence of robust governance is an empirical question that will be answered by WP3 second Report (D3.2) through the analyses of concrete cases of robust (and less robust) responses to

turbulence in the context of the economic, refugee and Covid-19 crisis in the Robust Consortium partner countries.

Hence, in this WP3 Report we have proposed a conceptualisation of multilevel governance as an instance of policymaking and a systematic typology of the possible configurations that interactivity can assume, laying down the basis for deepening our theoretical understanding of which varieties of multilevel governance are likely to be more conducive to the robust responses to crisis and why. These are still unanswered questions, that appear though of the utmost importance if the ultimate goal is that of strengthening the capacity of policymakers and public governors to pursue efficient solutions to recurrent crises while at the same time fulfilling principles of democratic legitimacy and accountability.

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